

PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF A MODERN TEACHER IN THE DIGITALIZATION OF EDUCATION

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Annotation:

The article discusses the problem approaches to teaching as a professional competence of a modern teacher in the globalization and digitalization of education

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The concept of "approach" from the point of view of S. I. Ozhegov is a set of effective techniques and adequate methods in the process of influencing someone or studying something [3, p.76].

Considering the term "approach" in relation to the pedagogical sphere of activity allows us to accept its multiple meanings. Thus, approach acts as a worldview category reflecting the totality of social attitudes of the subject of education and training, acting as a bearer of social consciousness, correlated with the concept of "position." [1, p. 24] From the point of view of theoretical "affiliation," knowledge about approaches to cognition should be attributed to methodological knowledge, which allows us to say that their understanding lies outside the boundaries of pedagogical methodology, and therefore requires a special refraction within the framework of the topic of this study.

Along with the above, the approach can be conceptualized as a unified, systemically organized set of educational and upbringing processes, uniting the subjects of pedagogical interaction, represented as structural and functional elements. If we examine the above interpretations, we find no obvious

contradictions. However, we should note the existing differences in their semantic content, which reflect different levels of application in practical activities. However, despite the above, it should be emphasized that in the proposed interpretations, the term "approach" defines specific value guidelines for education and upbringing.

According to the assumption put forward by E.G. Yudin, four levels should be distinguished in the structure of methodological knowledge, namely:

- 1) philosophical; 2) general scientific; 3) concrete scientific;
- 4) technological. The content of the first (philosophical) of these levels is the general principles of cognition and the categorical structure of science as a whole. The second level—General scientific methodology is represented by theoretical concepts applicable to virtually all scientific disciplines. Specific scientific methodology, as the third level, encompasses a set of research methods, principles, and procedures in a specific scientific discipline, including issues specific to a particular area of scientific knowledge and those affecting higher levels of methodology. Finally, the fourth level, technological methodology, encompasses research methods and techniques capable of obtaining reliable empirical data and, after processing, incorporating it into the body of scientific knowledge. Let us examine scientific approaches in more detail in the context of this study.

Thus, philosophy serves as the objective basis for the development of any pedagogical ideas, establishing the general direction and method of understanding a given phenomenon, including pedagogical ones. It is precisely this philosophy that recognizes the systems approach as the universal approach to scientific analysis (I. V. Blauberg, V. N. Sadovsky, E. G. Yudin, L. von Bertalanffy, A. D. Hall, R. I. Fagin).[9].

According to A. G. Kuznetsova, the main characteristics that should be noted in the systems approach include:

- 1) reproduction; 2) diversity and dynamism of relations; 3) unity of objective

and subjective; 4) complex internal structure; 5) predictability and designability; 6) predictability; 7) self-organization; 8) controllability; 9) reflection; 10) value orientation; 10) vector; 11) uniqueness; 12) diversity [2, p.34].

According to T. A. Ilyina's definition, a system is an ordered set of closely interrelated elements, identified based on specific characteristics and united by a common functional goal and indivisible control, interacting with the environment to form a holistic phenomenon. This definition of a system allows it to be symbolically represented as a formula:

$$\Sigma: \{M\}, \{x\}, F,$$

(1) where {M} is the set of system components; {x} is the set of relationships between them; F is a new property of the system that characterizes its integrity and completeness.

From the above it follows that in order to get answers to the questions it is necessary to “take” an interdisciplinary point of view[4, p.57].

Following the logic of our reasoning and aligning it with the topic of our research, we can hypothesize that any innovative processes taking place in educational practice must be linked to existing pedagogical systems. This allows us to apply the basic principles of a systems approach in this study.

The significance of using a systems approach in our research lies in its ability to clarify the definition of the research object and develop an adequate methodology for its study. Based on the interpretation of the concept of "culture" within the context of the stated research topic, we can recognize its systemic essence, systemic parameters, and properties, which requires its consideration in terms of system-wide characteristics, the processes occurring within it, and the uncovering of the logic of their subsequent transformations. The application of a systems approach can, in fact, ensure the integration of specific aspects of knowledge from various fields of knowledge involved in the study of culture, which will ultimately enable us to solve

the stated problems. Relying on the guiding principles of this approach will allow for the most complete integration of knowledge, incorporating the most diverse theoretical and specific research materials.

Thus, a systems approach will allow us to ensure the integrity of the presentation of the phenomenon of information culture under study, to overcome the current isolation of its consideration by introducing a unified methodological base that allows for the integration of its traditional components, such as information literacy, information readiness, readiness for information interaction, etc., thereby realizing, taking into account the thesis “the whole is always greater than the sum of its parts,” a more “qualitative” understanding of “information culture.”

However, the development of human personality can be related to a multifaceted, multilevel, and nonlinear system, which presupposes the movement of foundations and the periodic shifting of determinants. In this study, we elaborated on this premise by adding the process of assimilation and transmission of information, which, along with the gender- and age-specific developmental characteristics of schoolchildren, affirms the priority of various determinant relationships at the level of the subjects under consideration.

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